

Fire evacuation drills in schools: Using Minecraft VR, Unity VR, or Video?

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ABSTRACT

Live training for disaster preparedness in schools can be time-consuming, expensive, difficult to manage at scale, and in some cases, dangerous. Training using VR (Virtual Reality) applications promises to be more affordable, safer, and capable of supporting a wider range of scenarios. But creating a realistic VR application requires time and specialized competence in programming and 3D modelling. This paper investigates whether highly realistic VR applications are necessary for effective preparedness training or if simpler, more accessible solutions suffice. To test this, we compare three training environments for navigating an evacuation route in a university building: a Unity-based VR environment, a Minecraft-based VR environment, and a video presentation of the route, followed by a real evacuation of the same route. While the video-based evacuation was considered the most effective training in this case, especially Minecraft shows great promises, although not significantly better than Unity. Further studies are needed to better understand the integration and the role of technologies in school evacuations.

Keywords

Fire evacuation, Training, VR, Unity, Minecraft, Video, Case, Exploratory study

INTRODUCTION

Performing evacuation procedures at schools and universities for training purposes can be challenging due to coordination, resource allocation, and responsibility assignment (Fazeli et al., 2024). Such training often involves activating the fire alarm and asking people to evacuate the building. Usually, this is based on 2-3 evacuation exercises per year, sometimes with additional opportunities for employees to practice using a fire extinguisher. For guidelines and procedures, besides documents and regulations, instructions on web pages or posted on walls are typically available. Simulations by using VR, mixed realities or serious games can offer novel ways to experience evacuation scenarios (de Carvalho et al., 2022; Smith & Ericson, 2009; Tasnim et al., 2025) nowadays. However, which technologies to choose and how to effectively perform and implement evacuation in schools in daily routines requires further exploration.

This paper explores how different technologies can contribute to fire evacuation training in a university building and whether more realistic VR applications are necessary or if simpler, more accessible solutions can be used for effective evacuation training.

In this paper, we define *more realistic* broadly to include applications that more accurately depict physical

environments, objects, and interactions. Consequently, Unity, with its libraries for object representation and interaction, can offer a higher degree of realism compared to the cubic environment characteristic of Minecraft. However, Minecraft, with around 30 million active players per day as of 25.02.2026 (Minecraft users, 2026, Woodward, 2026), can reach more users, and due to many children's familiarity with this platform, its users may be more easily involved and creatively contribute, not only to understanding but also to actively creating new learning situations for evacuation. For creating *more-realistic* VR games, the Unity game engine (Unity, 2026) and the Unreal game engine (Epic Games, 2026) are natural choices today. They are both well-established and mature platforms. We have chosen the Unity game engine, as in our experience, it has better documentation and a lower learning curve than the Unreal engine. To create a *less-realistic* VR game, we have chosen the Minecraft platform (Minecraft, 2026) with an extension that enables it to run in VR (Vivecraft, 2026). We contrast the two VR games with video training in the same case study of evacuating a university building. The results are based on observations and questionnaire data from 21 subjects.

There are several studies that motivated us to investigate the role of realism, implementation possibilities and effects of technologies for school evacuations. The practical use of VR for fire emergency training is primarily for professionals today, according to our knowledge. A recent study (Tasnim et al., 2025) found only one school that systematically included VR training in its education. In a meta-review of 52 studies, Scorgie et al. argue that VR-based training adds value to traditional safety training across multiple dimensions, including engagement, realism, and preparedness, while noting challenges such as motion sickness and limited reporting on long-term training outcomes (Scorgie et al., 2024). Another review, based on 37 papers focusing on VR drills (Gagliardi et al., 2023), argues for the potential of VR applications to support evacuation drills, but these are mostly in developers' laboratories due to users' dizziness, lack of engagement, and lack of realism. While VR can offer higher user experiences, often measured as presence, this does not necessarily lead to more learning (Makransky et al., 2020), and the design elements in a VR application are not tightly connected to learning theories and learning outcomes (Radianti et al., 2020). High-fidelity VR simulations that deliver great experiences can be costly and time-consuming to produce (Mergen, 2024). Work by Zhang et al., (2025) comparing a VR and a non-VR fire evacuation simulation showed that both VR and non-VR can be effective at simulating a real-world emergency, but VR simulation score higher on, e.g., presence and the generation of real feelings such as anxiety.

While voices from the public, and some research, argue for providing more realistic simulations for evacuations, it is not completely clear what *realism* means in a project, both for object and environment simulations (Alessi, 1988), or regarding the interaction (Bonfert et al., 2024). Since simulation is in time, Lorusso et al. (2022) focus on realism, specifically the flow in a given situation. They use Unity for VR and graphics, and a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulator for real-time simulation of fire and smoke, a crowd dynamics simulator, and walking pads in a school building setting. Mystakidis (Mystakidis et al., 2022) also use Unity, coupled with a CFD simulator, in a school fire setting.

Using Minecraft for training is less common, but there are some recent examples. Gampell et al. (2024) show how students use Minecraft without VR to both model parts of the environment and play/train in the model. Interactive modelling and multiplayer mode are two strong features integrated into the Minecraft game system. Zhang et al. (2023) use a similar application for single-room evacuation, examining participants' behavior and how they maneuver around a fire to exit the room. A Minecraft game designed to teach players about a healthy diet is presented in (Aigner et al., 2024). They conclude that their Minecraft game has the potential to influence behavioral change. The positive experiences from these studies motivated our use of a Minecraft-based training simulator and our investigation of its capability to engage and use school students.

STUDY DESIGN

This paper presents a case-based exploratory study, in which a learning activity is examined through four complementary explorations. The learning activity resulted from exploring fire evacuation training through Minecraft with VR, Unity with VR, video, and running drills as if real fire alarms had gone off. The study design follows a similar structure to that of Kaae and her colleagues (Kaae et al., 2010), except that data were collected through observations and questionnaires rather than interviews. According to Kaae, this design is suitable for early-stage inquiry aimed at identifying promising directions for future, more targeted research. Information about the task, participants, data collection, and technology used is presented in the following subsections.

Task

For our comparison, we have chosen a fire evacuation scenario from a university building, as it is important to our students and does not require simulating complex phenomena or interactions with the environment. This increased the chance that we would be able to represent the scenario sufficiently in Minecraft, which has a more

limited ability to tailor it than Unity, and to make videos and perform real-life evacuations in a reasonable time. The evacuation was from the 4th floor of the university (see Figure 1) to the exit on the ground floor. Participants were asked to exit the building in a controlled manner, without running, and to follow the exit signs. A strategically placed fire obstacle in a staircase increased the difficulty by forcing participants to take a more complex path, allowing us to gather more behavioral data. The fire obstacles were represented in the real-life evacuation by stopping the participants if they tried to enter an area where there was a fire in the VR simulation. The task and the results interpretation were discussed with a firefighter. See also Figure labelled “Collage” in the Appendix for images along the whole route from Minecraft, Unity, and Video.

Figure 1. Diagram of the exit route from “START” on the 4th floor to “END” on the first floor. The green and blue lines show the correct path out, where blue indicates walking in stairs. The red circles show where exit signs would be visible to a person walking. There are three fire symbols indicating locations with fire. The 4th floor has two fires, so the staircase to the right is totally blocked. There is also a fire on the stairs between the 3rd and the 2nd floor. This forced the walker to navigate to the other staircase on the 3rd floor. When that staircase was found, the walker could use it all the way to the 1st floor. Without the fire in the staircase, the path would have been trivial, requiring only walking down the stairs all the way from the fourth floor. The black, thick lines show where we added artificial walls to constrain possible movement in the building for limiting the scenario.

Participants

After training in one of the three modalities (Unity, Minecraft, and video), the participants completed a questionnaire and were tested by performing a real evacuation to measure their evacuation time. For establishing a common ground for comparison, one group of subjects performed the real evacuation without prior training.

Data was collected from 21 participants, six for Unity, seven for Minecraft, five for video, and three for performing evacuation without prior Unity, Minecraft, or video training. Five of the Minecraft trainees performed a live evacuation. In Unity, seven individuals trained and answered the questions, and five performed the live evacuation. For video, there were five individuals performing the training and the live evacuation, but only 3 out of them answered the questions. Therefore, the video average scores on the questions have a lower degree of representability/confidence.

Data collection

Observations were made to measure overall performance during the evacuation experiences via a 24-item questionnaire (see Figure 2 in Appendix). The questions focused on overall experience and performance, with questions on presence, emotion, engagement, immersion, flow, and usability, focusing separately on how the participants experienced the usability of context, tasks, and the used technology (Heldal, 2007). The questionnaire was built up considering usability focusing on effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction within a specified context (ISO 9241-11, 2018). The questionnaires used a 5-point Likert scale, from 1 (worst) through 3 (neutral) to 5 (best), modified after the immersive tendency questionnaire of Witmer and Singer (1998) and included the possibility to answer in text for some questions.

Four subjects also tried the other VR simulator after having tried both the first one and the real evacuation. They were given a comparative questionnaire, designed around the 24 original questions, to evaluate Unity and Minecraft relative to each other rather than just evaluating a simulator engine by itself. These results mostly supported the trend of the original questions, and we did not find additional insights from them.

Technologies used

We use the Unity game engine for the more realistic training simulator and Minecraft for the less realistic VR training simulator. Minecraft does not inherently support VR, but with an extension or “mod” (Minecraft terminology and short for modification) called Vivecraft (2026) that enables Minecraft use in VR. Both versions modeled the same evacuation route. We also included a video walkthrough of the fire evacuation escape route as a third kind of training, so we could compare a basic non-VR ‘simulation’ with the two VR simulations.

We deliberately used Minecraft without any programming or scripting for this study to more clearly contrast it with the programming required in Unity. In a similar manner, Jarvis et al. (Jarvis et al. 2021) contrasted the use of Unity as a simple alternative to an advanced in-house developed VR engine, noting that the recent availability of powerful 3D game engines has created new opportunities for implementing VR systems. Perhaps, with software like Minecraft, we are now seeing another step in this direction, and the contours of democratizing the implementation of VR systems, where non-programmers, even children, can create them.

Creating the school environment in Minecraft took about 8 hours in total. The limited building blocks of Minecraft result in very quick, but coarse modelling of the environment. Making the video was trivial and took less than 10 minutes.

For the Unity version, it took about 2 weeks (75 hours) of modelling, and about 2 weeks (75 hours) of programming for a master student in computer science, with some background in computer graphics and in Unity. The students estimated that an expert in modelling would use half of the modelling time, and that an expert in Unity game development for 3D and VR games would use half or one third of the programming time.

For the development of the Unity version, several factors influence the required time. Substantial familiarity with mathematics, game development and the Unity ecosystem is necessary. Tasks such as navigating the editor, understanding component-based design, importing and configuring packages, working with prefabs, setting up VR interactions (e.g., doors and physics), and using tools such as ProBuilder for modelling introduce a considerable learning curve. Unity provides significantly greater flexibility and customization compared to simpler platforms, but this flexibility also increases development complexity. Even extending the project with features such as multiplayer introduces additional challenges, including object state synchronization and networking logic, which typically require programming and domain knowledge.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The following results present performance measures and aggregated qualitative experiences from the training, based on questionnaire responses.

Measured training effect

To measure the training effect of Unity, Minecraft, and Video, we report the time taken for the real evacuation in Figure 3. The group that performed the evacuation with no *prior* training is labeled “no training.”

Figure 3. Real evacuation timings in seconds for the different groups. Each individual is plotted with a point and its timing is shown. The four colored column heights, along with the bold numbers above, show the average timing for each group. The black vertical line indicates the interval between the minimum and maximum timing values.

Unity and Minecraft timings yielded results similar to those of the no prior training group, indicating that there was no or little measurable training effect on evacuation time for the VR solutions. The video group had the fastest evacuation times. Our hypothesis is that video performed best because it revealed the exact path one had to follow. We also observed that the live evacuation timings were highly correlated with the subject's walking speed. The decision-making part, i.e., the time spent locating the next exit sign as soon as the first had been reached, was much shorter than the locomotion part, i.e., the time spent walking between the exit signs. Therefore, we believe our real-life experiment was not well-designed to measure the potential training effects of the different VR simulators. A firefighter we discussed this result with suggested that a difference might have appeared if the subjects had been exposed to more stress during the test, such as during a real fire.

Questionnaire results

This Section presents a brief summary of the results from the questionnaire (see Figure 2 in Appendix for all questions and answers). The aim is that this data should provide more tangible insights into the experience of using the different technologies. We use the following abbreviations: question number X (qX), Minecraft (M), Unity (U) and video (V). When we present the results of a question, we provide the average value for the answers. We sort the answers from best to worst, e.g., the answers of q16 are V5 U4 M3.5, which means that the average response on the Likert scale was highest for video (5), followed by Unity (4) and Minecraft (3.5). Questions are grouped together in topics and discussed in the following subsections.

Perceived training effect

Although the live training timing measurements did not provide clear information on the training effects of Minecraft and Unity, we believe q16 and q24 capture participants' perceived training effects, where q16 was: *I feel better prepared to find the way out*, and q24 was: *I feel better prepared now*.

q16 had scores V5 U4 M3.5. We see that scores for both VR simulators are above 3 and thus show a perceived positive effect, but video training scored best. q24 had scores V3.7, M3.5, and U3.1 and also here video scored best.

Studies have shown that *perceived* training effect correlates with *actual* training effect (Johnson & Marakas 2000, Mousavi 2023). This can indicate that both Unity and Minecraft VR training give actual training effects; this is further, examined in the Discussion section.

Experiencing entertainment and fun during training

This subsection presents the analysis of the questions aimed at measuring flow and participants' engagement during the training. This is done through q4: *It was entertaining/fun to do the training exercise*, q8: *I focused*

continuously on what I saw in VR (only for VR questions, omitted for the V question), and q9: *Time disappeared during training*.

q4 scored M4.7 U4 V2.7, q8 scored U4.4 M4.2 V4, and q9 scored U4.3 M3.8 V3.

The U and M scores for each question were greater than 3. V scores were the worst, sometimes below, or equal to 3. One can say that M and U were considered more entertaining and fun to train in, while V is the least appreciated and can even be boring (score less than 3 for q4)

Compared to the earlier category of perceived training effect, where V scored best, in this category of entertainment and fun, V scored worst. In both categories, M was highly appreciated, sometimes scoring even higher than U. Thus, in both categories, Minecraft does well and is sometimes better than Unity. This is an important observation, as developing a Minecraft solution offers many advantages over a Unity solution.

Experiencing nausea during training

This experience was measured via a direct question reporting nausea, q5: *I got nauseous of VR*. The results for q5 were M3.8 U3.1. One subject reported in text: *VR gives me a headache*. Getting nauseous with VR is a well-known problem, and it is present in both our VR solutions, since the average score was above 3. We did not ask video subjects about this, since we believe nausea is not a common problem for video.

Experiencing graphical realism

How people experience realism in Minecraft and Unity is measured in q6, q21, and q22. The questions were q6: *My experience of the VR-world matched that of the real world*, q21: *The quality of the graphics was good*, q22: *The quality of the graphics ruined the user experience*. Note that q22 is phrased negatively deliberately.

The answers were q6: U3.4 M2.8, q21: U3.6 M3.5, q22: U1.6 M2.2. For realism, Unity scores better than Minecraft, which is expected since the graphics quality of Unity is superior to that of Minecraft. A side-by-side image is shown in Figure 4. We can also see that M scored lower than 3 for q6, which may be interpreted as indicating that the M testers consider the M simulator more of a training tool than one that resembles reality. This is further emphasized in the next Section where we see M scores lower than U on presence.

Figure 4. Three depictions of the same location. Left. A photo of the place where the fire is observed, middle: Unity graphics, and right: Minecraft graphics. Notice the two escape signs shown in all three images, and the higher realism in the Unity graphics compared to the Minecraft graphics.

Experiencing presence in VR

According to the definition of presence in VR, presence refers to subjective feelings of being in the surrounding environment, interacting with objects, and solving tasks (Slater et al., 1994). For some studies, presence can be considered a subjective user experience. This feeling should be optimal in real life, even if a person likes or dislikes the surrounding environment, problems, and interactions. It is interesting for VR applications, here in Minecraft and Unity, to compare the presence in graphical environments to the optimal one, also in comparable live situations.

The following questions, q1, q2, q3, and q7, cover questions for approximating experienced presence. q1 is formulated as: *I felt that I was in virtual reality as if I were really there*. q2: *I felt feelings, just like in an evacuation exercise*, q3: *I felt feelings like I would have in a real evacuation*, and q7: *I felt like I was in a real evacuation*

The answers were q1: U3 V2.7 M2.4, q2: V2 U2 M1.7, q3: V2 U1.9 M1.7 (q3 with high spread for U), and q7: V2.7 U2.6 M1.7. For all questions, V scores high. It scores best on 3 out of 4 questions and second best on 1 question. Presence in U was reported to be always better than M. However, all scores across all training types are low, with values equal to or below 3. For a follow-up experiment, it would be interesting to find out why these scored so low and to investigate which factors are necessary for increasing the feeling of presence.

Remaining questions

After the analysis of questions 10-15, the results are not reported, since they scored quite similarly and because these answers were not tightly related to the simulator technology itself. We have also chosen to omit questions 17-20 and question 23 for the same reason.

We can briefly note that for q17 (*The training helped me prepare to find the escape route*), q19 (*Interactions in VR were intuitive*), and q20 (*Interactions with the virtual environment were natural*), M has a higher score than U. According to our hypotheses, this may be due to weaknesses in our Unity implementation regarding navigation and interaction. The higher Minecraft scores could be related to the fact that in Minecraft, aspects such as navigation and interaction has been standardized and fine-tuned for its users.

DISCUSSION

Regarding the results for “perceived training effect”, studies have shown that perceived training effect represents actual training effect. Self-efficacy, defined by Bandura (1997), is the perceived confidence in succeeding in a task. Post-training self-efficacy has proven to be a useful predictor of task performance (Johnson & Marakas 2000). Therefore, the answers to questions 16 and 24 relating to self-efficacy may provide some evidence of the real training effect, which the timing data were unable to provide. Also, Mousavi et al. (2023) support this, finding that gains in self-efficacy correlate with the training effect.

Why did the video training score the highest for “Perceived training effect”? This might be because the video presented the actual solution for evacuating the building, so if the participant interpreted the question literally, it would be natural to give the highest score to the simulator that presented the escape route. Also, in (Mousavi et al., 2023), they reported stronger results for video than for VR. They thought this was due to their task being more knowledge-based than skill-based, which would also fit our scenario, as it was about the knowledge of the path out. An example of a skill-based situation is shown in the study by (Chan & Choy, 2025). They compared learning outcomes between students who used a custom-developed VR cooking game and those who watched video recordings of the same content. The tasks included preheating the oven, cracking eggs, separating the egg yolk from the egg white, whisking the eggs, and placing them on a baking tray. These are tasks that require planning and motor skills, which the VR simulator enables them to train. In that study, the VR training group showed superior learning compared to the Video group.

Integrating fire-safety training seamlessly into everyday education is essential for building a culture of preparedness, yet it remains difficult to achieve in practice. Traditional drills are often only used in laboratories or are too general, resource-intensive, and infrequent, so students rarely receive consistent, contextually rich training from these, and many students can only have a superficial understanding of the risks based on these (Tasnim et al., 2025). While the current study does not clearly indicate which technologies to embed or how to integrate fire-safety training more naturally into the educational environment, we illustrated the possibilities through concrete prototypes and problematized possible solutions.

CONCLUSIONS

This study showed comparative results from using three different technologies to train for fire evacuations. Video scored best on the important category, “*Perceived training effect*,” and well on all other categories except entertainment/fun, and therefore, at the present moment, this could be the best candidate for training when the scenario is knowledge-based (as opposed to skill-based) and can be presented as a video. This could be linked to a webpage where students can log in to learn more about emergency preparedness at their own school. Among the two VR simulators, Unity scored best. There was no significant difference between Unity and Minecraft, and, most importantly, they scored equally well on “*Perceived training effect*”. This may indicate that, for simulations that can be expressed within the current limits of Minecraft, it can be an effective alternative for creating training applications, in line with Zhang et al.’s (2023) studies. Our study has also shown that the use of less realistic graphics does not appear to negatively affect training for the evacuation scenario.

We hypothesize that it is the degree of interaction needed to increase one's skill that dictates which training medium (Unity, Minecraft, or Video) is most suited. For low-interaction use cases, video is superior because it shows the solution directly. For high interaction, such as in a cooking simulator (Chan & Choy, 2025), a solution that allows fine-grained control, such as Unity, is needed. For interactions that can be expressed in the more limited environment of Minecraft, Minecraft is well-suited due to its fast development speed, multiplayer support, distribution support, and popularity among young people.

FUTURE WORK

Building on the findings from the current work in progress, we will conduct a follow-up investigation using an updated version of the Minecraft and Unity applications. For this next phase, we are developing more complex yet pedagogically relevant evacuation tasks in which overall evacuation time is influenced less by walking speed and more by the participants' ability to solve meaningful problems encountered along the escape route. We plan to tender the Unity environment with increased visual realism through refined lighting configurations, while we will continue to explore the functional limits of Minecraft as a simulator or serious-game platform by incorporating custom behaviors through additional mods and scripting. One example currently under development is an advanced modelling tool in Minecraft that enables users to rapidly generate the environment to be evacuated by importing floor-plan images of a building. This follow-up study will also include an expanded set of background questions concerning participants' prior exposure to VR and Minecraft, as these factors may correlate with performance or questionnaire responses. Furthermore, participants will receive a more extensive introduction, including a structured training session on how to operate the respective VR applications, to ensure a more comparable baseline of familiarity with technology and thereby reduce variability in the results. Given Minecraft's strong cultural presence among younger users, we also consider it valuable to investigate non-VR Minecraft-based evacuation training, as learning about potential incidents, disasters, and evacuation procedures within familiar environments may enhance engagement and preparedness.

REFERENCES

- Aigner, C., Köck, K., Baranyi, R., Winkler, S., Weindl, K., & Grechenig, T. (2024). NutriMine – A serious game modification for Minecraft to support people keeping a healthy diet. *IEEE 12th International Conference on Serious Games and Applications for Health (SeGAH)* (pp. 1–7). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SeGAH61285.2024.10639569>
- Alessi, S. M. (1988). Fidelity in the design of instructional simulations. *Journal of Computer-Based Instruction*.
- Bandura, A. (1997). Self-efficacy: The exercise of control. W. H. Freeman/Times Books/Henry Holt & Co.
- Bonfert, M., Muender, T., McMahan, R. P., Steinicke, F., Bowman, D., Malaka, R., & Döring, T. (2024). The interaction fidelity model: A taxonomy to communicate the different aspects of fidelity in virtual reality. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 1-33.
- Chan, H.-Y., & Choy, S.-T. C. (2025). Using VR as a new pedagogical approach for food science and technology education in Hong Kong. *Proceedings of the European Conference on Games Based Learning (ECGBL)*. Academic Conferences International. <https://papers.academic-conferences.org/index.php/ecgbl/article/view/4178>
- de Carvalho, P. V. R., Ranauro, D. O., de Abreu Mol, A. C., Jatoba, A., & de Siqueira, A. P. L. (2022). Using serious game in public schools for training fire evacuation procedures. *International Journal of Serious Games*, 9(3), 125-139.
- Epic Games. (2026). *Unreal Engine* [Computer software]. <https://www.unrealengine.com/>
- Fazeli, S., Haghani, M., Mojtahedi, M., & Rashidi, T. H. (2024). The role of individual preparedness and behavioural training in natural hazards: A scoping review. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*.
- Gagliardi, E., Bernardini, G., Quagliarini, E., Schumacher, M., & Calvaresi, D. (2023). Characterization and future perspectives of virtual reality evacuation drills for safe built environments: A systematic literature review. *Safety Science*, 163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2023.106141>
- Gampell, A. V., Gaillard, J. C., Parsons, M., Le Dé, L., & Hinchliffe, G. (2024). Participatory Minecraft mapping: Fostering students' participation in disaster awareness. *Entertainment Computing*, 48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.entcom.2023.100605>
- Heldal, I. (2007). The impact of social interaction on usability for distributed virtual environments. *International Journal of Virtual Reality*, 6(3), 45–54.
- ISO 9241-11 (2018). *Ergonomics of human-system interaction Part 11: Usability: Definitions and concepts*. ISO 9241-11.
- Jarvis, C., Soltészova, V., Ulvang, D. M., Siccama, D., & Patel, D. (2021). Evolution of VR software and hardware for explosion and fire safety assessment and training. *Interactive Data Processing and 3D Visualization of the Solid Earth*. 273–290. Springer.
- Johnson, R. D., & Marakas, G. M. (2000). Research report: The role of behavioral modeling in computer skills acquisition: Toward refinement of the model. *Information Systems Research*, 11(4), 402–417.

- <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.11.4.402.11869>
- Kaae, S., Søndergaard, B., Haugbølle, L. S., & Traulsen, J. M. (2010). Development of a qualitative exploratory case study research method to explore sustained delivery of cognitive services. *Pharmacy World & Science*, 32(1), 36–42. DOI: [10.1007/s11096-009-9337-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11096-009-9337-5)
- Lorusso, P., De Iuliis, M., Marasco, S., Domaneschi, M., Cimellaro, G. P., & Villa, V. (2022). Fire emergency evacuation from a school building using an evolutionary virtual reality platform. *Buildings*, 12(2), 223. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12020223>
- Makransky, G., Andreasen, N. K., Baceviciute, S., & Mayer, R. E. (2020). Immersive virtual reality increases liking but not learning with a science simulation and generative learning strategies promote learning in immersive virtual reality. *Journal of Educational Psychology*.
- Mergen, M. (2024). Reviewing the current state of virtual reality integration in medical education: A scoping review. *BMC Medical Education*, 24, 5777. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-024-05777-5>
- Minecraft Mojang Studios. [Computer software] <https://www.minecraft.net/>
- Minecraft users. <https://playercounter.com/minecraft/>. (Accessed 25.02.2026).
- Mousavi, S. M. A., Powell, W., Louwse, M. M., & Hendrickson, A. T. (2023). Behavior and self-efficacy modulate learning in virtual reality simulations for training: A structural equation modeling approach. *Frontiers in Virtual Reality*, 4, 1250823. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frvir.2023.1250823>
- Mystakidis, S., Besharat, J., Papantzikos, G., Christopoulos, A., Stylios, C., Agorgianitis, S., & Tselentis, D. (2022). Design, development, and evaluation of a virtual reality serious game for school fire preparedness training. *Education Sciences*, 12(4), 281. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12040281>
- Radianti, J., Majchrzak, T. A., Fromm, J., & Wohlgenannt, I. (2020). A systematic review of immersive virtual reality applications for higher education: Design elements, lessons learned, and research agenda. *Computers & Education*, 147, 103778. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103778>
- Scorgie, D., Feng, Z., Paes, D., Parisi, F., Yiu, T. W., & Lovreglio, R. (2024). Virtual reality for safety training: A systematic literature review and meta-analysis. *Safety Science*, 171, 106372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2023.106372>
- Slater, M., Usoh, M., & Steed, A. (1994). Depth of presence in virtual environments. *Presence: Teleoperators & Virtual Environments*, 3(2), 130-144.
- Smith, S., & Ericson, E. (2009). Using immersive game-based virtual reality to teach fire-safety skills to children. *Virtual Reality*, 13(2), 87-99.
- Tasnim, R. K., Heldal, I., Patel, D., Murano, P., & Wijkmark, C. H. (2025). Implementing Virtual Reality for Fire Evacuation Preparedness at Schools. *Computers*, 14(7), 286.
- Unity Technologies. *Unity*. [Computer software] <https://unity.com/>
- Vivecraft. Virtual reality Minecraft for SteamVR. [Computer software] <https://www.vivecraft.org/>
- Witmer, B. G., & Singer, M. J. (1998). Measuring presence in virtual environments: A presence questionnaire. *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments*, 7(3), 225–240.
- Woodward, M. (2025). Minecraft user statistics (December). *Search Logistics*. <https://www.searchlogistics.com/learn/statistics/minecraft-user-statistics/>
- Zhang, Y., Paes, D., Feng, Z., Scorgie, D., He, P., & Lovreglio, R. (2025). Comparative analysis of fire evacuation decision-making in immersive vs. non-immersive virtual reality environments. *Automation in Construction*, 179, 106441. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2025.106441>
- Zhang, Z. C., Li, H. B., Lee, E. W. M., Ma, Y., Zhang, W. K., & Shi, M. (2023). Application of Minecraft in the study of evacuation dynamics under fire emergency conditions. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 624, 128935. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physa.2023.128935>

APPENDIX

Figure 2. This figure shows all questions, numbered 1 to 24, and their answers. Each individual answer is plotted with a point and given the same tag across all answers. The column heights and the numbers above in bold shows the average Likert score. The black vertical line shows the interval between the minimum and maximum score. A red M or a black U in the top left corner is displayed to show which out of M and M scores best on the question. Below is shown the result for the comparative question where 1 means preference for Minecraft and 5 means preference for Unity. Since 3 represents no preference, it is shown with a vertical stippled line and the center column is colored lighter to more easily see the trend by accentuating the non-neutral answers.

Figure “Collage”. Side-by-side pictures from Minecraft, Unity and the video tutorial for different positions along the route. The first row shows the staircase fire. The Minecraft fire can be partially seen, the Unity fire is clearly shown, while the hand in the video is there as part of communicating to the viewer to not to walk down due to a fire.